

ASSESSING SPEAKING ANXIETY AMONG EFL STUDENTS

Maliha Sania Fazal Hussain^{*1}, Dr. Fazal Hussain Shah²^{*1}Language Instructor M.A. English Jazan University²Consultant Surgeon MBBS, FCPS THQ Hospital, Darya Khan, Bhakkar^{*1}mfazal@jazanu.edu.sa, ²drazal3@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17626978>**Keywords**

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Corresponding Author: *

Maliha Sania Fazal Hussain

Abstract

Background: Learning English as a Foreign Language (EFL) is a significant source of anxiety for students in non-English speaking countries.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of speaking anxiety among female EFL students at Jazan University.

Study design: Cross sectional study

Place and duration of study: Department of English Language, Jazan University, Saudi Arabia, from 1st of October to 31st of December 2024.

Materials and Methods: This study included 120 female students with age range of 18 to 30 years. The students with any mental disorder, comorbid conditions and unwilling for consent were excluded. After obtaining informed written consent, all participants were assessed by Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS). Data analysis was performed using SPSS v. 25, with p-values <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean age was 24.13 ± 3.92 years. The average duration of educational tenure at the university was 12.45 ± 5.33 months. The unmarried females were predominant as 83 (69.2%) were unmarried. The mean FLCAS score was 103.18 ± 21.98 . The anxiety categorization showed that 49 (40.8%), 59 (49.2%) and 12 (10.0%) students experienced low, moderate and severe forms of anxiety respectively. The data stratification showed that students with <1 year study duration experienced increased levels of anxiety (p value 0.002).

Conclusion: Among the female university students, 59.2% had moderate and severe form of anxiety. It is advisable to conduct large, multicentre survey that account for potential confounding factors to validate these findings.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is a fundamental English language skill that students, including those in junior high school, should develop. It involves the oral use of language, requiring speakers to effectively organize information, utilize discourse markers, employ repetition and stress, among other elements. The goal of speaking activities is to convey information clearly to others.

In the English curriculum the students are mandated to master speaking skills and achieve a

score above the minimum passing grade, typically around 70-80, depending on institutional policies. However, speaking continues to pose challenges for many learners, particularly countries where English is not native. Limited time for word recall, pronunciation, intonation, and responses makes speaking one of the most challenging English skills to improve. These difficulties can interrupt speech flow and hinder effective communication.¹

Students who have navigated through the pivotal phase of their education often encounter numerous stressful events. The challenges at higher education levels are intensified by rigorous curricula, demanding assignments, and projects. It is imperative to recognize that mental well-being is just as crucial as physical health for students to thrive academically.² Educators play a vital role beyond imparting knowledge, as maintaining students' mental health is paramount.³ Anxiety disorder and depression are complex mental disorders that is prevalent worldwide. Its effects range from individual impairment to strained interpersonal relationships and hindered professional functioning. Moreover, depressive illness significantly impacts physical health through disruptions in sleep patterns, changes in food consumption, and reduced physical activity. Addressing depression and anxiety among students is advantageous at the individual, institutional, and societal levels.^{4,5}

Students commonly face challenges in English speaking activities, such as difficulty recalling words or responding, and feeling anxious when required to speak. Anxiety, defined as fear or concern about threatening or difficult situations, can hinder the ability to express oneself orally, leading to a lack of focus during speaking tasks. Approximately 25% of students spoke confidently, while others appeared nervous or afraid. The main sources of anxiety were concerns about making mistakes, particularly in grammar and pronunciation, and a lack of confidence in their English abilities.^{6,7} A study by Erdiana, N., et al. showed that 59% of students experienced moderate anxiety in speaking English as foreign language. The analysis in a study from Jordan identified several key sources of speaking anxiety in foreign language classrooms, including communication apprehension, self-assessment of language proficiency, teacher-learner interaction, insufficient vocabulary and knowledge of language rules, fear of course failure, and fear of negative evaluation. These factors contribute to students' discomfort and hinder their ability to speak confidently in English as a foreign language.⁷ To alleviate these issues, the study offers recommendations for EFL (English as a Foreign

Language) teachers. Firstly, teachers should create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves. Encouraging positive interactions between teachers and learners can help reduce anxiety levels. Additionally, teachers should focus on building students' vocabulary and language skills through engaging activities and practice exercises. Providing constructive feedback and reassurance can also help students overcome their fear of failure and develop confidence in their speaking abilities.

By addressing these sources of speaking anxiety and implementing these recommendations, EFL teachers can create a more conducive learning environment that supports students' speaking skill development and enhances their overall language proficiency.⁸ Previous research has also shown a significant number of students experiencing anxiety when speaking in front of others. Factors contributing to this anxiety include discomfort speaking in front of peers, fear of negative evaluation, and pressure to perform well.⁷ These findings indicate a need for interventions to reduce anxiety and improve students' speaking skills. Understanding the level of anxiety students experience in speaking English is crucial for educators to tailor lessons and provide support. By addressing these anxieties, educators can help students develop confidence and proficiency in spoken English.⁹

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of English Language, Jazan University, Saudi Arabia, over a one-month duration after obtaining approval from Ethical Review Committee (Reference No. REC-45/11/1095, Dated 12 May 2024). The study adhered to ethical principles, including respect for participant autonomy, privacy, and confidentiality. Written informed consent was secured from all participants before their inclusion in the study. The sample size of 120 subjects was calculated by WHO sample size calculator. The sample size was calculated based on a prevalence of speaking English anxiety among students at 59%⁴, with a confidence level of 95%, a margin of

error of 7%, and an additional 15% accounted for dropout. The sampling technique was non-probability consecutive sampling.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female students currently enrolled at Jazan University.
- Age range: 18–30 years.

Exclusion Criteria

- Students receiving treatment for any mental disorder.
- Students with known comorbid conditions, including diabetes, hypertension, or physical disabilities.
- Students unwilling to provide informed written consent.

After fulfilling eligible criteria, students were invited to participate. Each participant was provided with the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS)¹⁰ form for data collection. The FLCAS comprises 33 questions assessed on a 5-point Likert scale (SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neither Agree nor Disagree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree). Anxiety levels were categorized as follows:

- Scores ≤ 99 : Low anxiety
- Scores 99–132: Moderate anxiety
- Scores ≥ 132 : High anxiety

Participants were instructed on how to complete the FLCAS form and provided with assistance if

required. Completed forms were collected and recorded on a specially designed proforma.

The collected data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 for Microsoft Windows. Quantitative variables, including age, duration of stay at university, and FLCAS scores, were reported as means \pm standard deviations. Qualitative variables, such as marital status and levels of anxiety, were presented as frequencies and percentages. Effect modifiers like age, marital status, and duration of stay at university were managed through stratification. Post stratification, a Chi-square test was applied. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

At the end of our study period, we had the data of 120 female students. The mean age was 24.13 ± 3.92 years. The mean duration of stay at university was 12.45 ± 5.33 months. The unmarried females were predominant as 83 (69.2%) were unmarried (Figure I). Collectively, the FLCAS score was 103.18 ± 21.98 . The anxiety categorization showed that 49 (40.8%), 59 (49.2%) and 12 (10.0%) students experienced low, moderate and severe forms of anxiety respectively. The data stratification showed that there was no difference between age groups and marital status groups in terms of the anxiety levels (p value 0.856 and 0.724 respectively) while the duration of university showed that students with <1 year stay experienced increased levels of anxiety (p value 0.002, Table I).

FIGURES

Figure I. Marital status of students

Figure II. Anxiety levels among students

TABLES

Variable			Anxiety level			P value*
			Low	Moderate	Severe	
Age	<24 years	N	25	27	6	0.856
		%	43.1%	46.6%	10.3%	
	>24 years	N	24	32	6	
		%	38.7%	51.6%	9.7%	
Duration of study	<1 year	N	12	29	9	0.002
		%	24.0%	58.0%	18.0%	
	>1 year	N	37	30	3	
		%	52.9%	42.9%	4.3%	
Marital status	Married	N	17	17	3	0.724
		%	45.9%	45.9%	8.1%	
	Unmarried	N	32	42	9	
		%	38.6%	50.6%	10.8%	

Table I. Comparison among anxiety groups after stratification

DISCUSSION

At university level education, many students find it difficult to cope with the demands of higher education and responsibilities. The resultant anxiety can lead to variety of various disorders which can be up to severe form of depressive illness.² The prevalence of depression among university boys was estimated to be 28% and among girls 23%. The single students suffer more depressive illness versus the married ones (39% versus 20%).⁵ The EFL can further spice up the things in already anxiety prone study. Speaking anxiety is a critical issue in the domain of EFL

learning, as it significantly affects students' ability to communicate effectively. This form of anxiety is often associated with various emotional and psychological factors that hinder language acquisition and performance.^{4, 8} Depression and anxiety has been associated with the stigma among students which can aggravate the situation when it left unattended. The situation leads to burnout among EFL students.^{3, 11}

A Jordian study aimed to expand the limited research on speaking anxiety by identifying its causes among EFL university students in English classrooms. The key sources of speaking anxiety were the communication apprehension, students'

*
Chi square test

self-assessment of language proficiency, teacher-learner interaction, limited vocabulary, insufficient knowledge of language rules, fear of failing the course, and fear of negative evaluation.^{7, 12}

The collective Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) score served as a quantitative measure of anxiety, reflecting the overall emotional challenges faced by EFL students. This scoring system has been used for assessing and comparing anxiety levels in various researches on EFL.¹⁰ We used the same system for the assessment of the anxiety among students. Various other systems which involve some dynamic approaches to speaking anxiety have been mentioned in the literature. These scoring systems may fall into three categories; test-based scales for speaking anxiety, classroom-based scales for speaking anxiety, and activity-based scales for measuring L2 speaking anxiety.⁹ The use of scales which involve the other learning parameters can be even insightful like English Language Learning anxiety scale (ELLAS).⁶ But since our aim was to focus on the speaking anxiety so we had to adopt more selective scoring system.

Erdiana et al. investigated the levels of English-speaking anxiety experienced by EFL students in Indonesia. This research involved FLCAS scoring system to find the anxiety among students. The results showed that 38% experienced low levels of speaking anxiety, 59% displayed moderate levels of anxiety, and 3.4% reported high-level anxiety.⁴ In our study, we had the data of 120 students, in which the anxiety levels among students were found as low (49 participants, 40.8%), moderate (59 participants, 49.2%), and severe (12 participants, 10.0%). Factors such as age, marital status, and duration of exposure to the academic environment were evaluated. While age and marital status showed no significant impact, the duration of stay at the university emerged as a critical factor influencing anxiety levels, with newer students experiencing higher anxiety. Stratified analysis indicated no significant differences in anxiety levels across age groups or marital status categories ($p = 0.856$ and $p = 0.724$, respectively). However, students with a university tenure of less than one year exhibited significantly

higher anxiety levels compared to those with longer stays ($p = 0.002$). Our study highlights a significant prevalence of speaking anxiety among EFL students, categorized into low, moderate, and severe levels. This distribution provides insight into how anxiety is experienced across different individuals and subgroups, emphasizing the need for tailored interventions.

Speaking anxiety among EFL students is influenced by various interconnected factors that create hinderance in their language learning journey. The lack of confidence is considered primary contributor which is often rooted in inadequate vocabulary, pronunciation challenges, and limited exposure to conversational English. This leave students feeling unprepared for verbal interactions which is even more pronounced under stressful condition like exams. This anxiety is further aggravated by the fear of negative evaluation, where students dread making mistakes or being judged by their peers and instructors, particularly during oral exams, performance tasks and classroom discussions.^{4, 7}

In our study, the student who were studying in the university for more than one year had relatively less anxiety scores. This may be since after getting some time to adjust in the university may lead to emotional resilience. In a study, the participants who were more emotionally stable and exhibited higher levels of extraversion experienced less anxiety in the EFL classroom. Age emerged as a predictor, with older students demonstrating lower levels of anxiety scores as compared to their younger counterparts.¹

To alleviate speaking anxiety among EFL students' various interventions are helpful. The practical activities like presentation-based activity can be integrated into the curriculum to reduce the anxiety levels and enhance speaking skills.¹³ Incorporating mindfulness into educational practices gradually can have profound benefits, not only in reducing anxiety and boredom but also in fostering a supportive environment that nurtures an lead to reduction in the creative activities and educational progress. The integration of mindfulness and meditation practices can be helpful to overcome anxiety and boredom among EFL students.^{14, 15} The latest

technological advancements have been implicated to reduce the anxiety in EFL students with some well programmed algorithms.¹⁶

The impact of speaking anxiety on language learning is profound, as it creates psychological barriers that prevent students from fully engaging in speaking tasks and activities. This avoidance behaviour can further lead to reduced opportunities for practice thus creating a feedback loop, thereby slowing their improvement in oral communication skills. Over time, this cycle of avoidance and low performance can erode self-esteem, reinforcing the anxiety and further impedance in progress in language acquisition.^{4,8} Multifaceted approach is required to manage this significant issue among EFL students. Creating a supportive and non-judgmental classroom environment can be a helping hand to reduce the fear of making mistakes, while gradual exposure to speaking tasks, allows students to build confidence progressively. In the recent years, boom of technology, artificial intelligence, and language learning apps and online forums, offers a low-pressure platform for students to practice speaking skills which requires some degree of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Incorporating anxiety-management techniques, including mindfulness, relaxation exercises, and positive reinforcement, also help student to enhance learning capabilities. Together, these strategies can create a holistic framework for reducing speaking anxiety and empowering EFL students to achieve greater confidence in their language skills.^{14,17}

EFL students may experience anxiety, but this is often overshadowed by the overall development in their personalities. EFL contributes to various aspects of students' personality development and expressive abilities.^{18,19} The overall atmosphere of the institution and role of EFL teaching staff also plays significant role in the anxiety of the of students. The comprehensive approach involving teaching staff would provide more desirable outcomes while managing the anxiety among students. The intrinsic motivation and evaluative judgment from the teachers would provide feedback which will alleviate the anxiety of foreign language in speaking or writing.^{17,20,21} The results from a study by Liu, Y. and J. Wang demonstrated

that experienced and certified teachers employed coping strategies more frequently than their less experienced and non-certified counterparts for the management of EFL anxiety. These findings offer insights into the relationship between teacher's qualification and strategies which have theoretical implications for educational psychologists and applied linguistics researchers.²² The fact of anxiety, boredom and burnout of EFL teachers should be considered in mind whenever the curriculum is designed. The role of mediators would be a helping hand to optimize the situation.²³

A Chinese study found that using structural equation modelling, academic buoyancy emerged as a partial mediator in the relationship between EFL anxiety and behavioural engagement and as a complete mediator between English learning anxiety and agentic engagement.²⁴ Active Learning (AL) is an innovative instructional approach which is divergent from the traditional lecture based approach. The activities like problem-solving, discussions, and role-plays, the experimental group demonstrated significantly improved motivation, more positive attitudes toward English learning. It had significant impact on the reduction of anxiety scores as compared to control group among EFL students.²⁵

Limitations of the Study

The study may have limitations in terms of sample size and diversity, as anxiety levels can vary widely across different cultural and educational contexts. Moreover, the anxiety can present during any learning stage in EFL students. Our study focuses on speaking anxiety only, the reading, writing parts can be addressed in the future surveys also. There can be significant bias regarding self-reported data which can lead to underreport or overreport of anxiety levels.

Implications for Future Research

Further studies could adopt more robust approaches to explore longitudinal changes in speaking anxiety as students' progress through their EFL programs. Moreover, the role of cultural and linguistic background in speaking anxiety could provide deeper insights on further exploration. Technology-based tools or

personalized coaching can help educators design effective teaching methods to reduce anxiety and boost motivation.

CONCLUSION

Among female university students, 59.2% experienced moderate to severe anxiety. Large multicentre surveys that consider confounding factors are advised to validate these findings. Speaking anxiety significantly impacts EFL students' academic performance and language proficiency. Understanding these factors can help develop strategies to reduce anxiety levels. Combining supportive teaching, anxiety-management techniques, and innovative tools is crucial for helping EFL students overcome speaking anxiety and achieve fluency.

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